

Almost β -Regular Spaces and Almost $rg\beta$ -Closed Functions

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to introduce and study a new class of spaces, namely almost β -regular spaces which are generalizations of the concepts of almost regular spaces and β -regular spaces and to obtain some characterizations of almost β -regular spaces. Further, by using $rg\beta$ -closed sets, we define almost $rg\beta$ -closed functions and to obtain preservation theorems of almost β -regular spaces. The relationships among p -regular, β -regular, almost regular, almost p -regular, almost β -regular spaces are investigated. The main result of this paper is that almost β -regularity is preserved under M - β -open β - $rg\beta$ -closed surjective R -maps.

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1. Introduction

In 1969, Singal and Arya [20] introduced a weak form of regular spaces called almost regular spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 1970, Levine [6] introduced and studied generalized closed sets in general topology as a generalization of closed sets. This concept was found to be useful and many results in general topology were improved. In 1983, El-Deeb [5] introduced the notion of p -regular spaces by using p -open sets and obtained their characterizations and preservation theorems. In 1985, Mahmoud [7] introduced the concept of β -regular spaces. In 1990, Malghan and Navalagi [10] defined and studied almost p -regular spaces which were generalizations of both almost regular spaces and p -regular spaces. In 1993, palaniappan and Rao [16] introduced and studied regular generalized closed sets. In 1995, Dontchev [4] defined and investigated generalized β -closed sets. In 1998, Noiri [14] introduced rgp -closed sets and used these sets to obtain further characterizations of almost regular spaces and almost p -regular spaces. In 2005, Tahiliani [22] introduced generalized β -closed functions and obtained some new characterizations of β -regular spaces. Recently, by using β -closed sets, M. C. Sharma and Hamant Kumar [19] introduced almost β -closed functions.

In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of spaces, namely almost β -regular spaces and to obtain some characterizations of almost β -regular spaces. Further, by using $rg\beta$ -closed sets, we define β - $rg\beta$ -closed functions and to obtain preservation theorems of almost β -regular spaces. The relationships among p -regular, β -regular, almost regular, almost p -regular, almost β -regular spaces are investigated. The main result of this paper is that almost β -regularity is preserved under M - β -open β - $rg\beta$ -closed surjective R -maps.

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2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, τ) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $Cl(A)$ and $Int(A)$ respectively. A is said to be α -open [12] if $A \subset Int(Cl(Int(A)))$, p -open [11] if $A \subset Int(Cl(A))$, β -open [1] if $A \subset Cl(Int(Cl(A)))$. The complement of a α -open (respectively p -open, β -open) set is said to be α -closed (respectively p -closed, β -closed). The intersection of all α -closed (respectively p -closed, β -closed) sets containing A is called α -closure (respectively p -closure, β -closure) of A , and is denoted by $\alpha Cl(A)$ (respectively $pCl(A)$, $\beta Cl(A)$). The β -Interior [2] of A , denoted by $\beta Int(A)$, is defined as union of all β -open sets contained in A . The family of regularly open (respectively regularly closed, β -open, β -closed) sets of a space X is denoted by $RO(X)$ (respectively $RC(X)$, $\beta O(X)$, $\beta C(X)$). It is well known that $sCl(A) = A \cup Int(Cl(A))$, $sInt(A) = A \cap Cl(Int(A))$, $pCl = A \cup Cl(Int(A))$, $pInt(A) = A \cap Int(Cl(A))$, $\alpha Cl(A) = A \cup Cl(Int(Cl(A)))$, $\alpha Int(A) = A \cap Int(Cl(Int(A)))$, $\beta Cl(A) = A \cup Int(Cl(Int(A)))$ and $\beta Int(A) = A \cap Cl(Int(Cl(A)))$.

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a space (X, τ) is said to be

- (1). *generalized-closed (briefly g-closed) [6] if $Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.*
- (2). *regular generalized-closed (briefly rg-closed) [16] if $Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in RO(X)$.*
- (3). *α -generalized closed (briefly αg -closed) [9] if $\alpha Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.*
- (4). *regular generalized α -closed (briefly $rg\alpha$ -closed) [15] if $\alpha Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in RO(X)$.*
- (5). *generalized pre-closed (briefly gp-closed) [13] if $pCl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.*
- (6). *regular generalized pre-closed (briefly rgp-closed) [14] if $pCl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in RO(X)$.*
- (7). *generalized β -closed (briefly $g\beta$ -closed) [4] if $\beta Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.*
- (8). *regular generalized β -closed (briefly $rg\beta$ -closed) [17] if $\beta Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in RO(X)$.*
- (9). *g -open (respectively rg -open, αg -open, $rg\alpha$ -open, gp -open, rgp -open, $g\beta$ -open, $rg\beta$ -open) if the complement of A is g -closed (respectively rg -closed, αg -closed, $rg\alpha$ -closed, gp -closed, rgp -closed, $g\beta$ -closed, $rg\beta$ -closed).*

Remark 2.2. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \text{closed} & \Rightarrow & g\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & rg\text{-closed} \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow \\
 \alpha\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \alpha g\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & rg\alpha\text{-closed} \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow \\
 p\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & gp\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & rgp\text{-closed} \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow \\
 \beta\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & g\beta\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & rg\beta\text{-closed}
 \end{array}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 2.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$. Then the subset $A = \{b\}$ is g -closed as well as αg -closed but not closed.

Example 2.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a\}$ is $rg\beta$ -closed not g -closed.

Example 2.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, \}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a, b\}$ is g -closed as well as rg -closed.

Example 2.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a\}$ is α -closed as well as p -closed but not closed.

Example 2.7. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a, c\}$ is g -closed as well rg -closed. But it is not p -closed.

Example 2.8. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the subset $A = \{b\}$ is $rg\beta$ -closed not rg -closed.

Lemma 2.9 ([22]). Let A be a subset of a space X and $x \in X$. The following properties hold for $\beta Cl(A)$:

- (1). $x \in \beta Cl(A)$ if and only if $A \cap U \neq \phi$ for every $U \in \beta O(X)$ containing x .
- (2). A is β -closed if and only if $A = \beta Cl(A)$.
- (3). $\beta Cl(A) \subset \beta Cl(B)$ if $A \subset B$.
- (4). $\beta Cl(\beta Cl(A)) = \beta Cl(A)$.
- (5). $\beta Cl(A)$ is β -closed.

Lemma 2.10 ([22]). A subset A of a space X is $g\beta$ -open in X if and only if $F \subset \beta Int(A)$ whenever $F \subset A$ and F is closed in X .

Lemma 2.11 ([17]). A subset A of a space X is $rg\beta$ -open in X if and only if $F \subset \beta Int(A)$ whenever $F \subset A$ and $F \in RC(X)$.

3. Some Generalizations of Almost Closed Functions

Definition 3.1. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (a). strongly β -closed (respectively M - β -closed, β - $g\beta$ -closed [22], β - $rg\beta$ -closed) if $f(F)$ is closed (respectively β -closed, $g\beta$ -closed, $rg\beta$ -closed) in Y for every β -closed set F of X .
- (b). β -closed [1] (briefly $g\beta$ -closed [22], $rg\beta$ -closed) if $f(F)$ is β -closed (respectively $g\beta$ -closed, $rg\beta$ -closed) in Y for every closed set F of X .
- (c). almost closed [21] (briefly almost β -closed [19], almost $g\beta$ -closed, almost $rg\beta$ -closed) if $f(F)$ is closed (respectively β -closed, $g\beta$ -closed, $rg\beta$ -closed) in Y for every $A \in RC(X)$.

From the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ and $\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (X, \sigma)$ is closed as well as $rg\beta$ -closed.

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$ and $\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (X, \sigma)$ is almost closed as well as almost $rg\beta$ -closed.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ and $\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (X, \sigma)$ is M - β -closed as well as β -closed but not closed.

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ and $\sigma = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (X, \sigma)$ is β -closed as well as almost β -closed but not almost closed.

Theorem 3.6. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost β -closed (respectively almost $g\beta$ -closed, almost $rg\beta$ -closed) if and only if for each subset B of Y and each $U \in RO(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(B)$, there exists a β -open (respectively $g\beta$ -open, $rg\beta$ -open) set V of Y such that $B \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof. We prove only the first case; the proof of the others being entirely analogous.

Necessity: Suppose that f is almost β -closed. Let B be any subset of Y and $U \in RO(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(B)$. Put $V = Y - f(X - U)$ then V is a β -open set of Y such that $B \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Sufficiency: Let F be any regular closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(F)) \subset X - F$ and $X - F \in RO(X)$. There exists a β -open set V of Y such that $Y - f(F) \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset X - F$. Therefore, we have $f(F) = Y - V$ and $f(F)$ is β -closed in Y . This shows that f is almost β -closed. □

Theorem 3.7. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is β - $rg\beta$ -closed (respectively $rg\beta$ -closed) if and only if for each subset B of Y and each β -open (respectively open) set U of X containing $f^{-1}(B)$, there exists an $rg\beta$ -open set V of Y such that $B \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof. The proof is similar to that of Theorem 3.6 and is thus omitted. □

4. Almost β -regular Spaces

Definition 4.1. A space X is said to be

- (a). β -regular [7] (respectively p -regular [5]) if for each closed set A and each point $x \in X - A$, there exist disjoint β -open (respectively p -open) sets U, V such that $x \in U, A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.
- (b). almost regular [20] if for each $A \in RC(X)$ and each point $x \in X - A$, there exist disjoint open sets U, V such that $x \in U, A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.
- (c). almost β -regular (respectively almost p -regular [10]) if for each $A \in RC(X)$ and each point $x \in X - A$, there exist disjoint β -open (respectively p -open) sets U, V such that $x \in U, A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \text{regularity} & \Rightarrow & p\text{-regularity} & \Rightarrow & \beta\text{-regularity} \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow \\
 \text{almost regularity} & \Rightarrow & \text{almost } p\text{-regularity} & \Rightarrow & \text{almost } \beta\text{-regularity}
 \end{array}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 4.2. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Consider the closed set $\{b, c\}$ and a point 'a' such that $a \notin \{b, c\}$. Then $\{b, c\}$ and $\{a\}$ are open sets such that $\{b, c\} \subset \{b, c\}$, $a \in \{a\}$ and $\{b, c\} \cap \{a\} = \phi$. Similarly for the closed set $\{a\}$ and a point 'c' such that $c \notin \{a\}$. Then there exist open sets $\{a\}$ and $\{b, c\}$ such that $\{a\} \subset \{a\}$, $c \notin \{b, c\}$ and $\{a\} \cap \{b, c\} = \phi$. It follows that X is regular space.

Example 4.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the space X is β -regular but not p -regular, since for the closed set $\{b, c\}$ and the point $a \notin \{b, c\}$, there do not exist disjoint p -open sets containing them.

Example 4.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the space X is almost β -regular but it is not almost p -regular, since for the regular closed set $\{a, c\}$ and the point $b \notin \{a, c\}$, there do not exist disjoint p -open sets containing them.

Example 4.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then the space X is almost regular.

Theorem 4.6. The following properties are equivalent for a space X :

- (a). X is almost β -regular;
- (b). for each $F \in RC(X)$ and each point $x \in X - F$, there exists a β -open set U and an $rg\beta$ -open set V such that $x \in U$, $F \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.
- (c). for each $F \in RC(X)$, $F = \cap\{\beta Cl(V) : F \subset V \text{ and } V \text{ is } rg\beta - \text{open in } X\}$,
- (d). for each $F \in RC(X)$ and each nonempty subset A of X such that $A \cap F = \phi$, there exist $U \in \beta O(X)$ and an $rg\beta$ -open set V such that $A \cap U \neq \phi$, $F \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \phi$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b) The proof is obvious from the fact that β -openness implies $g\beta$ -openness and $g\beta$ -openness implies $rg\beta$ -openness.

(b) \Rightarrow (c) For any $F \in RC(X)$, we always have $F \subset \cap\{\beta Cl(V) : F \subset V \text{ and } V \text{ is } rg\beta - \text{open in } X\}$. Suppose that $x \in X - F$. By assumption, there exist a β -open set U and an $rg\beta$ -open set V such that $x \in U$, $F \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$. By Lemma 2.9, we have $x \in X - \beta Cl(V)$ and hence $x \in X - \cap\{\beta Cl(V) : F \subset V \text{ and } V \text{ is } rg\beta - \text{open in } X\}$. Therefore, we obtain $F \supset \cap\{\beta Cl(V) : F \subset V \text{ and } V \text{ is } rg\beta - \text{open in } X\}$ and hence $F = \cap\{\beta Cl(V) : F \subset V \text{ and } V \text{ is } rg\beta - \text{open in } X\}$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d) Let $F \in RC(X)$ and A be a nonempty subset of X such that $A \cap F = \phi$. Take a point $x \in A$ so that $x \in X - F$. Therefore, there exists an $rg\beta$ -open set V such that $F \subset V$ and $x \in X - \beta Cl(V)$. Now, put $U = X - \beta Cl(V)$, then we have $U \in \beta O(X)$, $A \cap U \neq \phi$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

(d) \Rightarrow (a) For each $F \in RC(X)$ and each point $x \in X - F$, there exists a β -open set U and an $rg\beta$ -open set V such that $x \in U$, $F \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$. Since $F \in RC(X)$, we have $F \subset \beta Int(V)$, $\beta Int(V) \in \beta O(X)$, and $U \cap \beta Int(V) = \phi$. This shows that X is almost β -regular. \square

Remark 4.7. We can obtain characterizations of almost β -regular spaces by replacing "V is $rg\beta$ -open" in (b), (c), and (d) of Theorem 4.6 with "V is $g\beta$ -open". The proof is quite similar to that of Theorem 4.6.

Theorem 4.8. Almost β -regularity is regular open hereditary.

Lemma 4.9. If Y is an open subspace of a space X and A is a subset of Y , then $\beta Cl_Y(A) = Y \cap \beta Cl(A)$.

Lemma 4.10. If Y is an open subspace of a space X and $A \in \beta O(X)$, then $A \cap Y \in \beta O(Y)$.

Theorem 4.11. If X is an almost β -regular space and Y is an open set of X , then the subspace Y is almost β -regular.

Proof. Let $G \in RO(Y)$ and $x \in G$. There exists $H \in RO(X)$ such that $G = Y \cap H$, since $G = Int_Y(Cl_Y(G)) = Int(Cl(G) \cap Y) = Int(Cl(G)) \cap Y$. Since X is almost β -regular, there exists $U \in \beta O(X)$ such that $x \in U \subset \beta Cl(U) \subset H$. We have $x \in U \cap Y \subset \beta Cl(U) \cap Y \subset H \cap Y$ and $U \cap Y \in \beta O(Y)$ by Lemma 4.10. By Lemma 4.9, we obtain $\beta Cl_Y(U \cap Y) = \beta Cl(U \cap Y) \cap Y \subset \beta Cl(U) \cap Y$ and hence $x \in U \cap Y \subset \beta Cl_Y(U \cap Y) \subset G$. Therefore, Y is almost β -regular. \square

Corollary 4.12. *If X is an almost β -regular space and X_0 is a regular open set of X , then the subspace X_0 is almost β -regular.*

5. Preservation Theorems

Definition 5.1. *A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be*

- (a). *almost continuous [21] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is open in X for every $V \in RO(Y)$,*
- (b). *R-map [3] if $f^{-1}(V) \in RO(X)$ for every $V \in RO(Y)$,*
- (c). *almost open [21] if $f(U)$ is open in Y for every $U \in RO(X)$,*
- (d). *M- β -open if $f(U) \in \beta O(Y)$ for every $U \in \beta O(X)$,*
- (e). *weakly open [18] if $f(U) \in Int(f(Cl(U)))$ for every open set U of X .*

Remark 5.2. *A R-map is also said to be regular irresolute by Palaniappan and Rao [16]. In [18], it was shown that almost openness implies weak openness but the converse is false.*

Theorem 5.3. *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost continuous and almost β -closed surjection with compact point inverses and X is regular, then Y is almost β -regular.*

Proof. Let F be a regular closed set of Y and $y \in Y - F$. We have $f^{-1}(Y) \cap f^{-1}(F) = \phi$. Since $f^{-1}(Y)$ is compact and $f^{-1}(F)$ is closed in the regular space X , there exist disjoint open sets U_0, V_0 of X such that $f^{-1}(Y) \subset U_0$ and $f^{-1}(F) \subset V_0$. Now, put $U = Int(Cl(U_0))$ and $V = Int(Cl(V_0))$, then U and V are disjoint regular open sets such that $f^{-1}(Y) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(F) \subset V$. Since f is almost β -closed, by Theorem 3.6, there exist β -open sets G, H of Y such that $y \in G, F \subset H, f^{-1}(G) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(H) \subset V$. Moreover, G and H are disjoint since U and V are disjoint. This shows that Y is almost β -regular. \square

Corollary 5.4. *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost continuous and β -closed surjection with compact point inverses and X is regular, then Y is almost β -regular.*

Theorem 5.5. *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an M- β -open β - $rg\beta$ -closed surjective R-map. If X is almost β -regular, then Y is almost β -regular.*

Proof. Let $F \in RC(Y)$ and $y \in Y - F$. Then $f^{-1}(Y)$ and $f^{-1}(F) = \phi$ are disjoint. Since f is an R-map, $f^{-1}(F)$ is regular closed in X . For each $x \in f^{-1}(Y)$, there exist disjoint β -open sets U and V of X such that $x \in U$ and $f^{-1}(F) \subset V$. Since f is M- β -open, we have $y = f(x) \in f(U)$ and $f(U) \in \beta O(Y)$. Since f is β - $rg\beta$ -closed, by Theorem 3.7, there exists an $rg\beta$ -open set W of Y such that $F \subset W$ and $f^{-1}(W) \subset V$. Since $f(U)$ and W are disjoint, by Theorem 4.6, we obtain that Y is almost β -regular. \square

Corollary 5.6. *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an almost continuous, almost open, M- β -open, M- β -closed function from an almost β -regular space X on to a space Y , then Y is almost β -regular.*

Proof. Every almost continuous almost open function is an R-map. Every M- β -closed function is β -rg β -closed and the proof follows immediately from Theorem 5.5. \square

Theorem 5.7. *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be continuous weakly open β -rg β -closed surjection and X is almost β -regular, then Y is almost β -regular.*

Proof. First we show that f is an R-map. Let V be any regular open set of Y . Since f is continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is open in X and hence $f^{-1}(V) \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(V)))$. Since f is a weakly open continuous surjection, we have $f(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(V)))) \subset \text{Int}[f(\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(V)))))] \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(f(f^{-1}(V)))) \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(V)) = V$. Therefore, we obtain $\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(V))) \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and hence $\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(V))) = f^{-1}(V)$. Thus, $f^{-1}(V)$ is regular open in X and f is an R-map. Next, we show that f is M- β -open. Let U be any β -open set in X . Then, we have $f(U) \subset f(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(U))) \subset \text{Int}[f(\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(U))))] \subset \text{Int}[f(\text{Cl}(U))] \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(f(U)))$. Therefore, $f(U)$ is β -open in Y and f is M- β -open. Theorem 5.5 completes the proof. \square

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of spaces, namely almost β -regular spaces and to obtain some characterizations of almost β -regular spaces. Further, by using β -closed sets, we define almost β -closed functions and to obtain preservation theorems of almost β -regular spaces. The relationships among p -regular, β -regular, almost regular, almost p -regular, almost β -regular spaces are investigated. The main result of this paper is that almost β -regularity is preserved under M- β -open β -rg β -closed surjective R-maps.

References

- [1] M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, S. N. EI Deeb and R. A. Mohamoud, *β -open sets and β -continuous mappings*, Bull. Fac. Assiut Univ. Sci., 12(1983), 77-90.
- [2] M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, R. A. Mahmoud, and E. R. Lashin, *β -closure and β -interior*, J. Fac. Edu. Ain Shams Univ., 10(1986), 235.
- [3] D. Carnahan, *Some properties related to compactness in topological spaces*, Ph. D. Thesis, Univ. of Arkansas, (1973).
- [4] J. Dontchev, *On generalizing semi- preopen sets*, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. (Math.), 16(1995), 35.
- [5] S. N. EI-Deeb, I. A. Hasanein, A. S. Mashhour and T. Noiri, *On p -regular spaces*, Bull. Math. Soc. Sci. Math. R. S. Roumanie (N. S.), 27(75)(4)(1983), 311-315.
- [6] N. Levine, *Generalized closed sets in topology*, Rend. Circ. Mat. Cityplace Palermo, 19(2)(1970), 89-96.
- [7] R. A. Mahmoud, M. E. Abd EI-Monsef and A. N. Geasia, *β -regular spaces*, Proc. Math. Phy. Soc. Egypt, 60(1985), 47.
- [8] R. A. Mahmoud and M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, *β -irresolute and β -topological invariant*, Proc. Pakistan Acad. Sci., 27(1990), 285.
- [9] H. Maki, R. Devi and K. Balachandran, *Associated Topologies of generalized α -closed sets and α -generalized closed sets*, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Ser. A Math., 15(1994), 51-63.
- [10] S. R. Malghan and G. B. Navalagi, *Almost p -regular, p -completely regular and almost p -completely regular spaces*, Bull. Math. Soc. Sci. Math. R. S. Roumanie, 34(82)(1990), 317-326.
- [11] A. S. Mashhour, M.E. Abd EI-Monsef and S. N. El-Deeb, *On precontinuous and weak precontinuous mappings*, Proc. Math. Phys. Soc. Egypt, 53(1982), 47-53.
- [12] O. Njastad, *On some class of nearly open sets*, Pacific. J. Math. , 15(1965), 961-970.

- [13] T. Noiri, H. Maki, and J. Umehera, *Generalized preclosed functions*, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Ser. A Math. (Math), 19(1998), 13.
- [14] T. Noiri, *Almost p -regular spaces and some functions*, Acta Math. Hungar., 79(3)(1998), 207-216.
- [15] T. Noiri, *Almost αg -closed functions and separation axioms*, Acta Math. Hungar., 82(3)(1999), 193-205.
- [16] N. Palaniappan and K. C. Rao, *Regular generalized closed sets*, Kyungpook Math. J., 33(1993), 211-219.
- [17] N. Palaniappan, *On regular generalized β -closed sets*, International Jour. of Sci. & Engg. Research, 4(4)(2013), 1410-1415.
- [18] D. A. Rose, *Weak openness and almost openness*, Internat. J. Math. Math. Sci., 7(1984), 35-40.
- [19] M. C. Sharma and Hamant Kumar, *Quasi β -normal spaces and $\pi g\beta$ -functions*, Acta Ciencia Indica, XXXVIII M(1)(2012), 149-154.
- [20] M. K. Singal and S. P. Arya, *On almost regular spaces*, Glasnik Math., 4(24)(1969), 89-99.
- [21] M. K. Singal and A. R. Singal, *Almost continuous mappings*, Yokohama Math. J., 16(1968), 63-73.
- [22] S. Tahiliani, *Generalized β -closed functions*, Bull. StateplaceCal. Math. Soc., 98(4)(2006), 367-376.